

Translaminar fracture toughness characterization in fiber-hybrid thin-ply composites: effect of hybridization

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Context : thin-ply prepreg

Regular preregs

Thin-ply preregs

Onset and strength, T800 carbon fiber, QI

Data reduction: J-integral

the integral DIC and high resolution cameras

- Cubic spline fitting and smoothing
- High quality derivatives

$\cdot \epsilon$

available at ScienceDirect
 Fracture Mechanics
<http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013794415001000>
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$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\dot{\epsilon} \right)$$

constar

J-integral data reduction of hierarchical thin-ply

ichaud^a

	E [GPa]	σ_{ult} [MPa]	ε_{ult} [%]
HR40	375	4410	1.1
34-700	234	4830	2.0

1. Fragmentation and pull-out

90° ply-block 0° ply-block

2. Extensive delamination and secondary damage

3. Crack bridging

Material selection

33L3A⁶⁰₁₂₀

90° ply-block 0° ply-block

33L4S⁶⁰₁₂₀

180 gsm

14L5A³⁰₁₈₀

210 gsm

33C2⁴⁵

45 gsm

Argyropoulos

10.00µm

25Y1⁹⁰

90 gsm

5 mm

40 mm

Offset: 0mm

25Y20⁹⁰

5 mm

40 mm

Offset: 2.5mm

Laminate thickness

- Architecture effects
- High scattering
- Deviations from linear scaling: hybrid effect?

- Need to decouple the two effects
- Hybrid effect = result different from expectations
- Comparison against a Rule of Mixture (RoM)

- Mild deviation from linear scaling
- Architecture effects

Initiation

Propagation

Mechanism : low-strain tow bridging

Energy vs. pull-out length

- Pull-out length drives the ERR

A dual-scale modelling approach

Identification of a traction-separation law

Output: energy dissipated by every bundle

- Hybridization effect
- Architecture effects
- Long bundles are much more dissipative

- Pull-out drives translaminar fracture toughness
- As ply-thickness decreases, pull-out length decreases
- Fiber-hybridization modulates pull-out length and density
- Translaminar toughness can be predicted according to pull-out distribution

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Questions?

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